

Near-Field Synthetic Aperture Interferometric Microwave Radiometry for Remote Sensing of Mines

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Abstract—A study was conducted for the use of a synthetic aperture interferometric radiometer (SAIR) for mine detection at near-field ranges using a 1.4-GHz laboratory prototype. Images of a buried aluminum plate, generated using a backprojection technique, are presented and compared to theory.

1. INTRODUCTION

The objective of this work was to determine the effectiveness of using a 1.4-GHz synthetic aperture interferometric radiometer (SAIR) for mine detection. To locate mines with radiometry, we take advantage of the fact that man-made items, especially those made of metal, will tend to reflect the low-level radiation from the sky and look like a “cold” object surrounded by “hot” soil. By using SAIR we can have high resolution without the problems associated with a single large antenna of a scanning radiometer. Measurements were made of 120 × 6 in. metal plates on and below the surface of the ground using an Army Research Laboratory (ARL) prototype SAIR with a 40-MHz bandwidth centered at 1.4 GHz.

2. PHENOMENOLOGY

A radiometer measures the natural radiation from a target, which is a combination of thermal emissions from the target itself and from reflected and scattered radiation from other thermal emitters. For mine location, the radiometer must have enough temperature resolution to see the temperature contrast between the mine and the soil. This contrast depends on many factors, the most influential being the target material or emissivity (ϵ), the depth to which the mine is buried, and the penetration depth of the soil, which ranges from 0.1 to 1 wavelength, depending on the moisture content of the soil [1]. To determine the difference in brightness temperature that a radiometer might see with and without a buried mine, we take the simplest case of a single homogeneous layer covering a metal surface. Taking into account dielectric losses and first-order

reflections, the difference in measured brightness temperature ΔT_m that the radiometer will measure with and without a mine present can be given by

$$\Delta T_m = T_1(1 - \Gamma_1) \left(\frac{1}{L_1^2} \right) + T_{\text{sky}} \left[-\frac{1}{L_1^2} (\Gamma_1^2 - 2\Gamma_1 + 1) \right]. \quad (1)$$

Figure 1 plots ΔT_m , using equation (1), as a function of loss factor for $T_1 = 300$ K, $T_{\text{sky}} = 6$ K [2], and a full range of reflectivity (Γ). Γ 's for soils at 1.4 GHz range from about 0.25 to 0.7 for volumetric soil moistures from 0 to 0.5 g cm⁻³ [3]. Modern SAIRs can detect ΔT 's on the order of a few degrees K; therefore, for soils in this range, we should be able to see mines buried up to 2δ ($\delta =$ penetration depth) (7.4 loss factor). Factors that reduce the ability to see buried mines include mines that are not highly reflective ($\Gamma_2 \ll 1$) of the sky temperature and a low fill factor. The fill factor is the percentage of the radiometer's antenna beam that the target fills.

Figure 1. ΔT_m for $\Gamma = 0.1$ – 0.9 as function of loss factor.

3. INTERFEROMETRIC IMAGING

A real aperture radiometer generates an image by scanning its antenna beam over a given field of view (FOV). The resolution is therefore determined by the antenna beam width. An SAIR generates its image from a synthetic aperture, and its resolution is determined by the synthetic aperture size. The resolution of ARL's one-dimensional array with antenna spaced every $\lambda/2$ can be given by [1]

$$\Delta\theta = \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{4}{2N+1}\right), \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta\theta$ = the angle between the first nulls in the antenna pattern and N = number of elements.

SAIRs measure the Fourier transform of the brightness temperature of the scene or the visibility function, and the image is indirectly obtained by the inverse Fourier transform of the visibility function. The interferometric measurements are made by cross-correlating the received signals of two spatially separated antennas, which are focused on the same area [4]. The sampled output of multiple pairs of antennas at different locations forms the visibility function. A numerical technique was developed for imaging a scene from the visibility, referred to as backprojection. Figure 2 shows the geometry of our system, where R_1 is the distance from the fixed antenna 1 to a point source located in the x - y plane, and R_d is the distance from antenna 2, positioned on the x axis a distance, d , from antenna 1. d is varied in increments of $\lambda/2$ up to a maximum array length or baseline, D . From the geometry in figure 2,

Figure 2. Geometry used to represent point source relative to antennas.

Figure 3. Backprojection images: (a) simulated and (b) measured point sources located 1.5 m in front of center of array. The $12 \times 12 \lambda$ images depict cross range horizontally centered at center of array and depict range vertically with bottom of image representing zero distance from array. Lighter gray represents higher brightness temperatures.

and

$$R_d = \sqrt{(|d| + x)^2 + y^2}. \quad (4)$$

The visibility function $V(d)$, or the output of the cross correlator, for a point source in the x - y plane is given by

$$V(d) = \cos\phi + j \sin\phi, \quad (5)$$

where $\phi = \frac{2\pi\Delta Rf}{c}$,

$$\Delta R = R_d - R_1,$$

f = frequency, and

c = speed of light.

Equation (5) can be calculated for a point source located in any position on the x - y plane. To form an image $I(x, y)$, we use

$$I(x, y) = \sum_{d=0}^D \frac{V(d)}{V(d, x, y)}, \quad (6)$$

where $V(d)$ in the numerator of equation (6) can be either a measured visibility function or the calculated visibility from equation (5) for a fixed point source at position (x, y) . The denominator $V(d, x, y)$ is calculated from equation (5) with (x, y) for the desired image pixel. d is the spacing between antenna pairs in multiples of $\lambda/2$, and D is some upper limit representing the largest aperture size or baseline. Images are generated by plotting the magnitude of $I(x, y)$ as a function of range (y) and cross range (x).

4. SIMULATIONS AND MODELING

Models were developed and used in conjunction with the imaging to produce simulated images of point sources and distributed scenes. $V(d)$ for point sources at any position on the x - y plane are calculated using equations (3), (4), and (5). Figure 3a shows a simulated image of a point source at the center of the SAIR's array, imaged using backprojection. To simulate the visibility function (V_n) for a distributed scene, we model the scene with multiple brightness temperatures and integrate over the scene. As an example, we will derive V_n for a scene with three distributed brightness temperatures, as depicted in figure 4. V_n is given by

$$V_n = \int_{-1}^1 T_B(x)P(x)e^{jnk_0 d_\sigma x} dx, \quad (7)$$

where $V_n = n$ th visibility,

$P(x)$ = element pattern, and

$T_B(x)$ = surface brightness temperature.

For $d_\sigma = \lambda/2$, $P(x) = 1$, and $T_B(x)$ as given in figure 4,

$$V_n = T_1 \int_{-1}^{x_a} e^{jn\pi x} dx + T_0 \int_{x_a}^{x_b} e^{jn\pi x} dx + T_1 \int_{x_b}^1 e^{jn\pi x} dx. \quad (8)$$

5. INSTRUMENTATION DESCRIPTION

ARL constructed an interferometric radiometer with an operating frequency of 1.4 GHz. The SAIR consists of two antennas, used to synthesize an array, and two microwave receivers, whose outputs are correlated. The synthetic aperture is synthesized using a rail that allows up to 25 different antenna locations separated by $\lambda/2$. A PC controls the position

Figure 4. Model of brightness temperature of metal strip on ground, T_1 = ground temperature, T_0 = reflected sky temperature from metal.

of the antenna and records the correlator output at many different antenna pair spacings or baselines, resulting in the visibility function (V_n). A sketch of the system is shown in figure 5.

6. NOISE SOURCE MEASUREMENTS AND COMPARISONS TO THEORY

Measurements were made of a point source, using 25 baselines, to verify the operation of the SAIR and processing. Figure 3b is a $12 \times 12 \lambda$ image generated using backprojection from the measured visibility data from a noise source placed 1.5 m away at the center of the array. A simulation is shown in figure 3a for comparison. The images obtained accurately depicted the noise source location, and the measurements are in good agreement with the simulations. The cross-range resolution in the images is about 1λ , which agrees with the theoretical resolution given by equation (2) of 1λ at a 1.5-m range.

7. MEASUREMENTS OF BURIED METAL PLATE AND COMPARISONS TO THEORY

Measurements were made, using 10 baselines, of a 6×120 in. metal plate, both directly on the soil and buried up to 3 in. at a range of 36 in. A long narrow object was used to increase the fill factor. An operational system would have a smaller antenna footprint in order to image mine-sized objects. Figure 6 compares the brightness temperature as a function of cross range for the metal plate buried in $1/4$ -in. increments up to $1-3/4$ in., at a position 36 in. from the array at an angle of 27 degrees to the right of center. The brightness temperature drops to the right of center, where the metal strip is located. A curve of bare ground is also shown for comparison. The curves in figure 6 show warmer temperatures for the plate buried 1 in. and deeper, and cooler temperatures for the plate buried under

Figure 5. Depiction of SAIR system and setup.

Figure 6. Brightness temperature as function of cross range for metal plate on surface and buried at depths from $\frac{1}{4}$ to $1\frac{3}{4}$ in.

an inch. The SAIR's sensitivity and/or stability are not high enough to differentiate between $\frac{1}{4}$ -in. depths. In figure 7, a comparison is made of the measured scene of a metal plate on the surface of the ground and a simulated scene using the brightness temperature model in figure 4. Figure 7 shows an agreement in cross-range position of the reflective metal. From these measurements, we concluded that the prototype SAIR is able to image a metal strip buried up to about an inch deep in the native soil. The theory discussed in section 2 predicted that we could see metal buried up to about 2δ , and with δ ranging from 0.1 to 1λ , we would expect to see 1- $\frac{5}{8}$ to 16 in.; since our soil was relatively dry, we would expect to see closer to 16 in. Two main factors limited the depth that we were able to see: the fill factor and the stability of the instrumentation. The reason that we were only able to see about an inch is mainly system instability: the system was not stable over the time it took to make the measurement. This has the effect of limiting our minimum detectable ΔT , therefore reducing the depth we were able to see. Future work will focus on improving the stability of our hardware.

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Figure 7. Comparison of measured and theoretical image of metal plate.

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